

COMPLEX QUANTUM STATE SPACE-TIME COSMOLOGY

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Abstract. We study the line element proposed by the quantum vacuum Kantowski-Sachs universe without cosmological constant. We consider the scale factor $b(= iR_I)$ of the metric to be imaginary and the other $a(= R)$ is real, of the Kantowski-Sachs quantum state space-time. It is seen, that in the Einstein's space-time, the numerical volume of the matter universe once been squeezed in a zero volume, we may assume then the matter universe transferred into another phase by the phase transition system. According to the classical theory it may be called an imaginary matter universe. It may be compared with the internal space 'a' of the extra-dimension 'D' expressed by the Kaluza-Klein cosmological universe.

So we think that the Einstein universe is numerically as a complex space-time rather than it was measured as only the real part classically.

Solving the metric tensors and getting the energy tensors $T_0^0 = T_1^1$ and $T_2^2 = T_3^3$ in the 10-dimensional space-time under the exchange $R_1 \leftrightarrow R$. The temperature would be measured before the phase transition. As we move towards the early stage of the liquid matter universe, we would find the matter energy wave length decreases but the amplitude increases. Ultimately the liquid matter universe transfers to vapour phase through the phase transition system. Then it may be found the wave length will increase in the opposite direction and the amplitude decreases as usual. The energy is then, may be called as latent energy wave. We introduce a wider universe, other than Einstein universe. We derived Einstein universe from wider universe.

1. Introduction. In 1915 Einstein published the general theory of relativity. He expected the universe to be 'closed' and to be filled with matter. Hence a new type of solution other than Schwarzschild solution is therefore needed to describe a universe filled everywhere with matter. Einstein published such a solution in 1917. Shortly after Einstein published his equations of general relativity, Karl Schwarzschild solved them to find the space-time geometry outside a spherical distribution of matter. The problem solved by Schwarzschild is basically a local problem, in the sense but the distortions of space-time geometry from the Minkowski geometry of special relativity gradually diminish to zero as we move further and further away from the gravitating sphere. In general any space-time geometry generated by a local distribution of matter is expected to have this property. Even from Newtonian gravity we expect an analogous result : that the gravitation field of a local distribution of matter will die away at a large distance from the distribution.

A Schwarzschild-type solution cannot therefore provide the correct space-time geometry of such a distribution of matter. Since we can never get away from gravitating matter. Before we consider Einstein's solutions, it is worth noting that more than two centuries earlier Newton also had attempted a solution describing a matter-filled universe of infinite extent. A highly symmetric distribution of matter does lead to a solution in Newtonian gravity. Newton found that such a universe would be static, for any particle of matter is being attracted equally in all directions, so it should stay put where it is.

On the other hand, homogeneity precludes any pressure gradients in the universe. And we know that any finite distribution of pressure-free matter would tend to shrink under its own gravity.

Newton also found his solutions to be unstable : any local inhomogeneity would precipitate gravitational contraction that would tend to augment the local inhomogeneity.

Edwin Hubble gathered the first evidence of the story in the early 1920's at the Mr. Wilson Observatory. By accurately measuring the distances of the nebulae, he showed that they were not only separate galaxies, but also that they all had a redshift, implying that they were all moving away from us. Hubble also observed that the further away the galaxy was, the larger was its redshift. In fact, the speed of recession of the galaxies, derived from the redshift, was proportional to their distance. It was soon realized that such an expanding universe was indeed predicted by mathematical models of the universe based on Einstein's general theory of relativity.

To construct model universe, using his newly developed general theory of relativity, one essential feature used by Einstein was the cosmological principle, which states that the universe is homogeneous and isotropic. In fact, if the universe is isotropic, it can be shown to be also homogeneous. Homogeneity means that the density is distributed uniformly throughout the universe. Although it was a bold and unsubstantiated assumption at the time, since one could then see the milky-way locally, it turns out to be an accurate one. Because on a larger scale, universe is found to be indeed homogeneous.

The generalized solution for the Einstein field equations for a homogeneous universe was first presented by Alexander Friedmann, and therefore bears his name. The Friedmann equation for the evolution of the cosmic scale factor $R(t)$ which represents the size of the universe, is

$$\left[\frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)} \right]^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho(t) - \frac{kc^2}{R^2(t)} \quad \text{i.e.,} \quad \dot{R}^2(t) = \frac{8\pi G}{3} [\rho(t) \cdot R^3(t)] \frac{1}{R(t)} - kc^2$$

Differentiating the above equation with respect to time, and since the total matter in a given expanding volume is unchanged, $[\rho(t) \cdot R^3(t)]$ is constant.

We have,

$$2\dot{R}(t)\ddot{R}(t) = -\frac{8\pi G}{3} [\rho(t)R^3(t)] \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R^2(t)}$$

i.e.,
$$\frac{\ddot{R}(t)}{R(t)} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}\rho(t)$$

Since $\ddot{R}$ is always negative, at a finite time in the past R must have been equal to zero. Then, according to these models, the contents of all the galaxies must have once been squeezed together in a small volume where the temperature would have been immensely high. The radiation left over from this fireball must still be around today, although cooled to a much lower temperature due to expansion of the universe.

It seems from the above discussion, the matter universe must have once been squeezed in a small volume.

An analogy will illustrate the scenario. Suppose steam is been cooled through the phase transition temperature of 100°C . Normally we expect the steam to condense to water at this temperature. However, it is possible to super-cool the steam to temperature below 100°C , although it is then in an unstable state. The instability set in when certain parts of the steam condense to droplets of water which then coalesce and eventually condensation is complete. In the super-cooled state the steam still remains its latent heat, which is released as the droplets form.

So it is in generally thought to be easier to imagine an unknown mechanism which would set vacuum parameter exactly to zero.

It we consider the $(4 + D)$ -dimensional Kaluza-Klein cosmology with a Robertson-Walker type metric having two scale factors 'a' and 'R', corresponding to D -dimensional internal space and 4-dimensional space, respectively. In the expansion of 'R'-universe, the internal space 'a' decreases as the space as R increases. Avoiding 'R'-universe squeezed in a zero volume, then we assume that the matter universe must be changed into another phase by the phase transition method with the help of latent energy.

So as the size 'R' of the Einstein matter universe numerically squeezed in a zero volume, then we may assume the size of the Einstein's matter universe become iR_I in other phase which can be measured classically, but it is only explained by the quantum cosmological theory, as the energy never die at all.

So we may consider the scale factor 'R' of the Einstein universe is only the real part and there may exist an imaginary part ' iR_I ' and hence the size of the universe is actually may be written in the form $R + iR_I$.

It is then compared with the D -dimensional internal space 'a' ($= iR_I$) of the Kaluza-Klein cosmology, with the Einstein's 4-dimensional space of the scale factor R . The knowledge about the quantum state space for the gravity system and gravity matter system are very limited and the definition of the innerproduct in quantum state space has not been found.

We apply proposal for vacuum and non-vacuum, closed Robertson-Walker space-time without cosmological constant and some unphysical states. It is found that the energy tensors T_k^i through Einstein tensors G_k^i and a measurement of temperature are related to the time exponentially.

2. Einstein field equation in complex quantum state. The work covered in the Einstein field equations did not tell us the important item of information about the universe is what happened, when the volume of the matter universe squeezed into zero volume and there before. To find the answer to this question it is necessary to do beyond the concept of Einstein universe. We need a new concept with the Einstein's universe to proceed any further, and Einstein's general relativity with complex space-time is one of the such theory. We will consider alternative approaches to cosmology but for the present is Kantowski-Sachs universe. We have the line element to start with :

$$ds^2 = -N^2(t)dt^2 + a^2(t)dr^2 + b^2(t)(d\theta^2 + \text{Sin}^2\theta d\phi^2) \quad (1)$$

The only nontrivial Einstein equations of the above metric (with $N = 1$ are)

$$\frac{\dot{b}^2}{b^2} + \frac{2\dot{a}\dot{b}}{ab} + \frac{1}{b^2} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_0^0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{2\ddot{b}}{b} + \frac{\dot{b}^2}{b^2} + \frac{1}{b^2} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_1^1 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} + \frac{\ddot{b}}{b} + \frac{\dot{a}\dot{b}}{ab} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_2^2 = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_3^3 \quad (4)$$

where c' is the velocity of photon-like particle in vapour stage and $c' > c$, the velocity of photon.

We next consider $a = R$ and $b = iR_I$, [where $i = \sqrt{-1}$]. Then the equation (2), (3) and (4) becomes

$$\frac{\dot{R}_1^2}{R_1^2} + \frac{2\dot{R}\dot{R}_1}{RR_1} - \frac{1}{R_1^2} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_0^0 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{2\ddot{R}_1}{R_1} + \frac{\dot{R}_1^2}{R_1^2} - \frac{1}{R_1^2} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c'^4}T_1^1 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{R}}{R} + \frac{\dot{R}_1}{R_1} - \frac{\dot{R}\dot{R}_1}{RR_1} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_2^2 = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_3^3 \quad (7)$$

Before we consider specific forms of T_k^i , it is worth noting that three properties must be satisfied by the energy tensor in the present framework of cosmology. The first is obviously define negative pressure by $T_2^2 = T_3^3$. The second T_0^0 , is define the matter energy density and the third T_1^1 is define the latent energy density. When $T_1^1 = 0$, then we have from the equation (6) is

$$2R_1\ddot{R}_1 + \dot{R}_1^2 - 1 = 0$$

Integrating, we get

$$R_1(1 - \dot{R}_1^2) = A \quad (8)$$

where A is the integration constant.

Again from (8), we get

$$\dot{R}_1 = \pm \sqrt{\frac{R_1 - A^2}{R_1}}$$

Integrating, we get

$$t = \pm \sqrt{R_1 - A^2} \cdot \sqrt{R_1} + A^2 \log |\sqrt{R_1} + \sqrt{R_1 - A^2}| + B \quad (9)$$

where B is the integration constant.

If $T_2^2 = T_3^3 = 0$, then

$$\frac{\ddot{R}}{R} + \frac{\ddot{R}_1}{R_1} + \frac{\dot{R}\dot{R}_1}{RR_1} = 0 \quad (10)$$

If $R_I \leftrightarrow R$ then $\frac{2\ddot{R}}{R} + \frac{\dot{R}^2}{R^2} = 0$ i.e., $t = (R^{3/2} - E)/D$ where D, E are integration constant.

3. Cosmology with complex scale factor. Consider the metric in which the space-time is assumed to be of Robertson-Walker type having a complex scale factor $R + iR_I$, where the scale factor R stands for (3 + 1)-dimensional space-time and iR_I ($= a$) is that for the internal space with dimension, Avoiding the imaginary term, the line element can be expressed in the form

$$ds^2 = -N^2(t)dt^2 + R^2(t) \frac{dx^i dx^j}{\left(1 + \frac{kr^2}{4}\right)^2} + a^2(t) \frac{dt^a dy^b}{(1 + k'\rho^2)} \quad (11)$$

where $N(t)$ is the lapse function, $r^2 = x^i x^i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), $\rho^2 = y^a \cdot y^a$ ($a = 1, 2, 3, \dots, D$) and $k, k' = 0, \pm 1$, for flat, closed or open type of 4-dimensional universe and D -dimensional space. For simplicity, we assume the internal space to be flat i.e., $k' = 0$.

The form of energy-momentum tensor is chosen as

$$T_{AB} = (-\rho, p, p, p, p_D, p_D, \dots, p_D) \quad (12)$$

Now, we examine the case for which the pressure along all the extra-dimensions vanishes, namely, $p_D = 0$. In doing so, we are motivated by the brane world scenarios where the matter is to be confined to the 4-dimensional universe, i.e., auxiliary hyper-space. So that all components of T_{AB} is set to zero but the space-time components and it means no matter escapes through the extra dimensions.

We assume the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ to be that of an exotic fluid with the equation of state

$$p_\chi = \left(\frac{m}{3} - 1\right) \rho_\chi \quad (13)$$

where p_χ and ρ_χ are the pressure and density of the fluid, respectively and the parameter m is restricted to the range $0 \leq m \leq 2$ so that there is violation of strong energy condition and the universe experiences accelerated expansion.

The scalar curvature corresponding to the metric (11) has the expression

$$R = \frac{-6RR_1N\ddot{R} + 6RR_1\dot{N}\dot{R} - 2R^2\ddot{R}_1N + 2R^2\dot{N}\dot{R}_1 - 2R_1N^3k + R_1N^3k^2r^2 - 6R_1N\dot{R}^2 - 6R\dot{R}\dot{R}_1N}{R^2N^3R_1} \quad (14)$$

Now substituting it into the dimensionally extended Einstein-Hilbert action (without higher dimensional cosmological term) including a matter term indicating the above mentioned exotic fluid the effective Lagrangian becomes

$$L = i^D \left[\frac{1}{2N} RR_1^D \dot{R}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12N} R^3 R_1^{D-2} \dot{R}_1^2 + \frac{D}{2N} R^2 R_1^{D-1} \dot{R}\dot{R}_1 - \frac{1}{2} k N R R_1^D + \frac{1}{6} N \rho_\chi R^3 R_1^D \right] \quad (15)$$

where dot represents the derivative with respect to t . We shall show an equivalence between ($k = 1$) and ($k = 0$) universes which are favoured by observations. The continuity equation, by using the contracted Bianchi identity in $(4 + D)$ dimensions, namely

$$\nabla_M G^{MN} = \nabla_M T^{MN} = 0 \quad (16)$$

together with the assumption that the matter is confined to $(3 + 1)$ dimensional space time gives $\nabla_i T^{ij} = 0$

$$\text{i.e., } \dot{\rho}_\chi R + 3(\rho_\chi + p_\chi)\dot{R} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Using (24) into the continuity equation (28), the energy density in a closed ($k = 1$) Friedmann-Robertson-Walker universe

$$\text{i.e., } \rho_{\chi}(R) = \rho_{\chi}(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)^m \quad (18)$$

where R_0 is the value of R at an arbitrary reference time t_0 .

Again, if we believe that the cosmological term plays an important role in vacuum energy density; then we may define the cosmological term as $\Lambda = \rho_{\chi}(R)$.

$$\text{i.e., } L = i^D \left[\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2N} R R_1^D \dot{R}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12N} R^3 R_1^{D-2} \dot{R}_1^2 \\ & + \frac{D}{2N} R^2 R_1^{D-1} \dot{R} \dot{R}_1 - \frac{1}{2} N R R_1^D + \frac{1}{6} N \Lambda R^3 R_1^D \end{aligned} \right] \quad (19)$$

with

$$\Lambda(R) = \Lambda(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)^m \quad (20)$$

Taking $m = 2$ and $\Lambda(R_0)R_0^2 = 3$

We have

$$\Lambda(R) = \frac{3}{R^2} \quad (21)$$

The lapse function $N(t)$, is an arbitrary function of time due to the fact that Einstein's general relativity is a reparametrization invariant theory. We therefore, take the gauge

$$N(t) = R^3(t) R_1^D(t) i^D, \quad (22)$$

and then Lagrangian (19) become

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\dot{R}^2}{R^2} + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \frac{\dot{R}_1^2}{R_1^2} + \frac{D}{2} \frac{\dot{R} \dot{R}_1}{R R_1} \quad (23)$$

We now defined the new variables

$$X = \log R \quad Y = \log R_1 \quad (24)$$

Then the equation (23) becomes

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \dot{X}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \dot{Y}^2 + \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} \dot{Y} \quad (25)$$

The equations of motion are obtained

$$\ddot{X} + \frac{D}{2}\ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$\ddot{X} + \frac{D-1}{2}\ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (26a)$$

Solving equation (26) and (26a) we get,

$$\ddot{X} = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\text{and } \ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (28)$$

The solutions for X and Y from equations (27) and (28) are

$$X = At + \gamma, \quad Y = Bt + \delta$$

$$\therefore R(t) = A'e^{\alpha t} \quad \text{and} \quad R_I(t) = B'e^{\beta t}$$

where the constants, A, B, γ and δ or A', B', α and β should be obtained from the initial conditions.

Consider the size of all spatial dimensions be the same at $t = 0$ and assumed that this size would be the planck size ℓ_p in accordance with quantum cosmological considerations.

So we take

$$R(0) = R_I(0) = \ell_p$$

so that

$$A' = B' = \ell_p$$

Thus

$$R(t) = \ell_p e^{\alpha t} \quad \text{and} \quad R_I(t) = \ell_p e^{\beta t}$$

It is important to note that the constants α, β are not independent and a relation may be obtained between them. This is done by imposing the zero energy condition $H = 0$ which is the well-known result in cosmology due to the existence of arbitrary laps function $N(t)$ in the theory. The Hamiltonian constraint is obtained through the legender transformation of the Lagrangian (25)

$$H = \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12}\beta^2 + \frac{D}{2}\alpha\beta = 0 \quad (29)$$

This constraint is satisfied only for $\alpha \leq 0, \beta \geq 0$ or $\alpha \geq 0, \beta \leq 0$. To find α, β , we first obtained and Hubble parameter for $R(t)$. Again $H_I = \frac{\dot{R}_I}{R_I} = \beta$ and the Hubble parameter $H_R = \frac{\dot{R}}{R} = \alpha$ by which the constant α is fixed.

$$\therefore R(t) = \ell_p e^{H_R t}, \quad R_I(t) = \ell_p e^{-H_R t} \quad (30)$$

for $D = 1$ also, if $\alpha \neq 0$, then $\alpha = -\beta$ or $\alpha + \beta = 0$, or $\dot{X} + \dot{Y} = 0$, $X + Y = \text{constant}$, or $\log R + \log R_I = \text{constant}$,

$$\therefore RR_I = \text{constant}.$$

Again, for $D \neq 1$, then either $\alpha = 0$ or $\beta = 0$

$$\therefore \dot{X} = 0 \text{ or } \dot{Y} = 0, \quad \therefore X = \text{constant}, \quad Y = \text{constnat}.$$

$$R = R_I = \ell_p \text{ (a time independent scale factor)}$$

Therefore,

For $D > 1$, then

$$\alpha_{\pm} = \frac{D\beta}{2} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D}\right)} \right] \quad (31)$$

$$\text{i.e., } H_{R_{\pm}} = \frac{DH_1}{2} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D}\right)} \right]$$

$$\therefore R_I(t) = \ell_p e^{H_I t}$$

4. Quantum cosmology over complex space. Quantum cosmology explain in appropriate quantum mechanical description of the universe, which was introduced and developed by DeWitt. In quantum cosmology the universe, as a whole, is treated quantum mechanically and is described by a single wave function $\Psi(h_{ij}, \phi)$, defined on a manifold (super space) of all possible three geometries and all matter field configurations. The wave function $\Psi(h_{ij}, \phi)$, has no explicit time dependence due to the fact that there is no real time parameter external to the universe. Therefore, there is no Schrodinger wave equation but the operator version of the Hamiltonian constraint of the Dirac-canonical quantization procedure, namely vanishing of the variation of the Einstein-Hillbert action S with respect to the arbitrary lapse function N .

$$H = \frac{\delta s}{\delta N} = 0$$

Which is written as

$$\hat{H}\Psi(h_{ij}, \phi) = 0. \quad (32)$$

this equation is known as the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) equation. The goal of quantum cosmology by solving the WDW equation over the complex space $R + iR_I$ is to understand the origin and evolution of the universe.

In principle, it is very difficult to solve the WDW equation in the super space due to the large number of degrees of freedom. In practice, one has a freeze out of all but a finite number of degrees of freedom of the gravitational and matter fields. This procedure is known as quantization in mini-super-space, and will be used in the following.

The mini-super-space in our model is two dimensional with gravitational variables X and Y . To obtain the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, in this mini-super-space. We start with the Lagrangian (25). The conjugate momenta corresponding to X and Y are obtained

$$P_X = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{X}} = \dot{X} + \frac{D}{2} \dot{Y} \quad (33)$$

$$P_Y = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{Y}} = \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} + \frac{D(D-1)}{6} \dot{Y} \quad (34)$$

From which we obtain

$$\dot{X} = \frac{6}{D+2} \left[P_X \left(\frac{1-D}{3} \right) + P_Y \right] \quad (35)$$

$$\dot{Y} = \frac{6}{D(D-1)} \left[P_Y \frac{2(1-D)}{D+2} - P_X \frac{D(1-D)}{D+2} \right] \quad (36)$$

Substituting equations (35) and (36) into the Hamiltonian constrain (29) which obtained through the legender transformation of Lagrangian (25)

$$H = (1-D)P_X^2 - \frac{6}{D}P_Y^2 + 6P_X P_Y = 0 \quad (37)$$

Now, we may use the following quantum mechanical replacements

$$P_X \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial X}, \quad P_Y \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial Y}$$

by which the Wheeler-DeWitt equation is obtained

$$\left[(D-1) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial X^2} + \frac{6}{D} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Y^2} - 6 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \Psi(X, Y) = 0 \quad (38)$$

Where $\Psi(X, Y)$ is the wave function of the universe in the (X, Y) mini-super-space.

The general solution is

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_D(R, R_I) = \phi_1 \left[\log \left\{ R^{3D+\sqrt{3D^2+6D}} R_I^{D(D-1)} \right\} \right] \\ + \phi_2 \left[\log \left\{ R^{3D-\sqrt{3D^2+6D}} R_I^{D(D-1)} \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Now for $\Psi_D(R, R_I) \leftrightarrow \Psi_D(R_I, R)$, we have $3D \pm \sqrt{3D^2 + 6D} = D(D - 1)$

$$\text{i.e., } D = 1 \text{ or, } 6 \quad \because D \neq 1 \text{ i.e., } D = 6$$

Thus, we take for $D > 1$, $R = \ell_p e^{H_R t}$ and $R_I = \ell_p e^{H_I t}$

Hence from (5), (6) and (7), we get

$$T_0^0 = \frac{c'^4}{8\pi g} \left(\frac{e^{-2H_I t}}{\ell_p^2} - H_I^2 - 2H_I H_R \right) \quad (40)$$

$$T_1^1 = \frac{c'^4}{8\pi G} \left(\frac{e^{-2H_I t}}{\ell_p^2} - 3H_I^2 \right) \quad (41)$$

$$\text{and } T_2^2 = T_3^3 = -\frac{c'^4}{8\pi G} (H_R^2 + H_I^2 + H_R H_I) \quad (42)$$

Now, it is clear that, when $H_R = H_I$ then $R = R_I$. Which is possible for $6 + 4 = 10$ dimensional space-time. Then the equations (40) and (41) are identical

$$\text{i.e., } T_0^0 = T_1^1 = -\frac{3c'^4}{8\pi G} \left(H_R^2 - \frac{e^{-2H_R t}}{3\ell_p^2} \right) \quad (43)$$

$$\text{and } T_2^2 = T_3^3 = -\frac{3c'^4}{8\pi G} (H_R^2) = -\frac{3c'^4}{8\pi G} (H_I^2) \quad (44)$$

Now, if $T_2^2 = T_3^3 = 0$ then, $H_I = H_R = 0$ i.e., $R_I = \text{constant}$. Hence there is a maximum of R_I

At $T_0^0 = T_1^1 = 0$ we have,

$$T = \frac{1}{H_R} \log \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3} \cdot \ell_p H_R} \right) \quad (45)$$

which is not possible, i.e., $T_0^0 = T_1^1 \neq 0$.

For derivation it is convenient to write

$$T_0^0 = T_1^1 = \varepsilon = -\frac{3c'^4}{8\pi G} \left(H_R^2 - \frac{1}{3\ell_p^2} e^{-2H_R t} \right) \quad (46)$$

$$\text{and } T_2^2 = T_3^3 = -p = \frac{3c'^4}{8\pi G} H_R^2 \quad (47)$$

It relates the pressure p to the energy density ε . Hence from equation (46) and (47) we have

$$\varepsilon + p = \frac{1}{8\pi G \ell_p^2} e^{-2H_R t} \quad [\text{consider, } c' = 1] \quad (48)$$

5. Behaviour of Entropy in the Complex Space-Time. The second law of thermodynamics tell us that the entropy in a given volume S^3 stays constant as the volume expands adiabatically.

That means $p + \varepsilon = \frac{\sigma T}{S^3}$, where σ is a constant and T is the temperature. Where S is the scale factor.

Assume,

$$S = R + iR_I = (1 + i)R \quad [\text{Since } R = R_I] \quad (49)$$

Hence,

$$\varepsilon + p = \frac{\sigma T}{R^3} \frac{1}{(1 + i)^3} = -\frac{\sigma T}{4R^3} (1 + i)$$

Separating real and imaginary part, we get

$$\varepsilon + p = -\frac{\sigma T}{4R^3} \quad (50)$$

Hence from equations (48) and (50) we have

$$-\frac{\sigma T}{4R^3} = \frac{e^{-2H_R t}}{8\pi G \ell_p^2}$$

$$\text{i.e., } T = -\frac{\ell_p}{2\pi\sigma G} e^{H_R t} \quad [\text{using (30)}]$$

We take $T = T_0$ (say) when $t = 0$.

Then

$$T = T_0 e^{H_R t} \quad (51)$$

Which is the temperature of the universe in the super gravity stage, when the wave function is symmetric under the exchange $R \leftrightarrow R_I$.

One may assume a sudden drop of temperature due to the separation of latent energy in the phase transition, which is not measurable by any physical instrument.

6. Einsteins solution in general phase without cosmological constant. Imagine, an uniform distribution of matter filling the infinite Euclidean space in a phase other than Einsteins universe. We know that any finite distribution of pressure-free matter would tend to shrink under its own gravity.

We consider the closed surface from the very early universe as rectangular-parallelepiped after than a cubical box and then spherical space-time. The equation of the diagonal of the parallelepiped as

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 = r_2^2 \quad (52)$$

Consider the side of the cubical box is r_1 and also consider the diagonal remains unchanged for parallelepiped and cubical box.

Hence the diagonal of the cubical box $\sqrt{3}r_1$

So

$$r_2 = \sqrt{3}r_1 \quad (53)$$

Now we consider the equation (63) of a 3-surface in Cartesian co-ordinates x_1, x_2, x_3 and x_4 by

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 = S_1^2 \quad (54)$$

Where S_1 is the radius of the 3-surface of a four dimensional hyper-sphere. We consider the total mater in the cubical surface and Einstein's spherical surface remains unaltered.

Hence $r_1^3 \varepsilon_1 = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \varepsilon$

$$\text{i.e., } r_1 = \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}\right)^{1/3} R \quad (55)$$

[Taking only the real part]

$$\therefore r_2 = \sqrt{3}r_1 = \sqrt{3} \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}\right)^{1/3} R \quad (56)$$

Interms of a constant negative curvature, the equation (54) becomes

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 - x_4^2 = -S_1^2 \quad (57)$$

Here,

$$S_1 = r_2 = \phi(t) \cdot R(t)$$

Where,

$$\phi(t) = \sqrt{3} \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}\right)^{1/3} \quad (58)$$

Where $\varepsilon, \varepsilon_1$ are the energy densities of the two phase respectively. Comparing with the Einstein's universe, the most general line element satisfying the Weyl postulate and the cosmological principal is given by

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - S^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \text{Sin}^2\theta d\phi^2) \right] \quad (59)$$

Where, $S(t) = \phi(t) \cdot R(t)$; $|\phi(t)| \geq \sqrt{3} \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/3}$

And the Einstein's equations becomes

$$2\frac{\ddot{S}}{S} + \frac{\dot{S}^2 + kc'^2}{S^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{c'^2} T_1^1 = \frac{8\pi G}{c'^2} T_2^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{c'^2} T_3^3 \quad (60)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{\dot{S}^2 + kc'^2}{S^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3c'^2} T_0^0 \quad (61)$$

where, $S(t) = \phi(t) \cdot R(t)$

$$\dot{S} = \dot{\phi}(t)R(t) + \dot{R}(t)\phi \quad (62)$$

$$\ddot{S} = \ddot{\phi}(t)R(t) + 2\dot{R}(t)\dot{\phi}(t) + \ddot{R}(t)\phi(t)$$

7. Einstein Universe derived from wider universe. From the equation (60) and (61) we have the relation,

$$\frac{d}{ds}(\varepsilon_1 S^3) + 3p'S^2 = 0 \quad (63)$$

when $T_1^1 = T_2^2 = T_3^3 = -p'$ and $T_0^0 = \varepsilon_1$.

At the very early epoch, $p' = 0$, then

$$\varepsilon_1 S^3 = \text{constant.} \quad (64)$$

By the equation (62) we have $\varepsilon_1 \phi^3(t) \cdot R^3(t) = \text{constant}$

$$\text{i.e., } \varepsilon R^3 = \text{constant.}$$

Consider, when $R = R_0$, $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0$ then

$$\varepsilon R^3 = \varepsilon_0 R_0^3 \quad (65)$$

Which may be found by Einstein's universe at the early epoch when pressure $p = 0$, by using the Friedmann equations and with the help of Robertson-Walker line element.

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - R^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \text{Sin}^2\theta d\phi^2) \right] \quad (66)$$

Again in absence of any external forces, the velocity u^i satisfies the geodesic equation

$$\frac{du^i}{ds} + \Gamma_{k\ell}^i u^k u^\ell = 0 \quad (67)$$

Substitute $\Gamma_{k\ell}^i$ in the equation (59) gives the result

$$u^\mu S^2 = \text{constant.} \quad (68)$$

However, u^μ measures the velocity in the co-moving (r, θ, ϕ) co-ordinates, we have

$$u^\mu \phi^2(t) R^2(t) = \text{constant.} \quad (69)$$

Again, if we substitute Γ_{kl}^i in the equation (66) which gives the result

$$u^\mu R^2(t) = \text{constant.} \quad (70)$$

Now, if we compare (70) with (69), we (have) $\phi(t) = \text{constant.}$

$$\text{i.e., } \varepsilon_1(t) \propto \varepsilon(t) \quad (71)$$

Which indicates the large or small matter energy density in the vapour phase change to the large or small matter energy density in the liquid phase and hence it is found, an important fact, that the existence of discrete structure in the universe, ranging from galaxies to super-clusters.

Concluding Remarks. We use the metric of the Kantowski-Sachs universe and find a general solution as Friedmann solved the Einstein general relativity using Ricci tensors. Here we consider the lapse function $N(t) = 1$ and velocity of photon—like particle is c' , which is greater than the velocity of photon. We find the different energy tensors T_0^0 and T_1^1 and $T_2^2 = T_3^3$. We think is T_0^0 is the energy density due to the matter energy and T_1^1 is the energy density due to the latent energy and $T_2^2 = T_3^3$ is equal to the negative pressure. It is found in 10-dimensional supergravity, the energy tensors $T_0^0 = T_1^1$ is symmetric under the exchange of $R \leftrightarrow R_I$. We get the exponential relation between the temperature and time. The time is to be calculated when $T_1^1 = 0$. We think the deadline of the matter energy is -273°C . It is shown, at the early epoch, the pressure free ($p' = p = 0$) wider universe and Einstein's universe are identical. It is found that the existence of discrete structure in the universe, ranging from galaxies to super-clusters.

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References

- Appelquist, T.; Chodos, A. and Freund, P.G.O. (1986) : Modern Kaluza-Klein Theories, Frontiers in Physics m Series vol. 65, (Ed. Adison-Wesely). A.G. Riess et al., *Astrophys J.*, 560, 49(2001).

- Arnowitt, R.; Deser, S. and Misner, C.W. (1962) : Misner, Gravitation : An Introduction to current Research, edited by L. Witten, Wiley, New York.
- DeWitt, B.S. (1967) : Phys. Rev., **160**, 1113, D. Shadev, Phys. Lett. **B137**, 155 (1984).
- Einstein, A. and deSitter, W. (1932) : On the relation between the expansion and the mean density of the universe. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, (USA), **18**, 213.
- Einstein, Albert (1987) : Ideas and Opinions, Crown Publishers, New York, pp.348.
- Gross, David (1989) : Can we Scale the Planck Scale? Physics Today, June, 9.
- Guth, Alan H. (1997) : The Inflationary Universe, Addison-Wesley Co., Inc, Reading, Massachusetts.
- Halliwel, J.J. and Hawking, S.W. (1985) : The origin of structure in the universe, Phys. Rev., **D31**, 1777.
- Hawking, Stephen W. (1988 & 1999) : A Brief History of Time, Bantam Books. New York, pp.357, A.G. Rieas et al., *Astrophys. J.*, **560**, 49 (2001), pp.134.
- Hawking, S.W. (1984) : Phys. Lett. **134B**, 403; E. Baum, *ibid*, **133B**, 1885 (1983).
- Hawking, S.W. (1985) : The arrow of time in cosmology, *Phys. Rev.*, **D32**, 2489.1
- Hawking, S.W. and Hartle, J.B. (1983) : Wave function of the universe, Phys. Rev., **D28**, 2960.
- Hawking, S.W. (1984) : The quantum state of the universe, Nucl. Phys., **B239**, 257.
- Hawking, S.W. and Luttrell, J.C. (1984) : The isotropy of the universe, Phys. Lett., **B143**, 83.
- Hoyle, F.; Burbidge, G. and Narlikar, J.V. 1997) : *Mon. R. Astron. Soc.*, **286**, 173.
- Hoyle, F. and Narlikar, J.V. (1964) : A new theory of gravitation. *Proc. R. Soc.*, **A282**, 191.
- Hoyle, F. and Narlikar, J.V. (1996) : A conformal theory of gravitation. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, **A294**, 138.
- Kleppner, Daniel (1993) : The Gem of General Relativity, Physics Today, April, 9.
- Lemos, N.A. (1996) : J. Math. Phys., **37**, 1449. B. Schmidt et al., *Astrophys. J.*, **507**, 46 (1998).
- Linde, A. (1982) : Scalar field fluctuations in the expanding universe and the new inflationary scenario, Phys. Lett., **B116**, 335.
- Lopez, J.L. and Nanopoulos, D.V. (1996) : Mod. Phys. Lett., **A11**, 1, M. Ozer, M.O. Taha, Phys. Lett. **B171**, 363 (1986), A.M.M. Abdel-Rahman, Phys. Rev. **D45**, 3497 (1992).
- Mendez, v. and Pavon, D. (1996) : Gen. Rel. Grav., **28**, 697.
- Vishwakarma, A and R.G. (1997) : Class Quant, Grav. **14**, 945; W. Chen, Y.S. Wu, Phys. Rev., **D41**, 695 (1990); M.O. Calvao, et al., Phys. Rev., **D45**, 3869 (1992).
- Wudka, J. (1987) : **D35**, 3255; Phys. Rev., **D36**, 1036 (1987).

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